

Role of Career Commitment in Employee Job Satisfaction of Commercial Banks Employees of Sukkur Region @ Sukkur, Sindh Pakistan.

Author's Details:

- ⁽¹⁾**Kanwal Syed**-Research Scholar, Department of Public Administration SALU Khairpur, Sindh, Pakistan
⁽²⁾**Urooj Talpur**-Assistant Professor, Department of Economics, University of Sindh, Jamshoro, Pakistan-⁽³⁾**Dr. Khalid Noor Panhwar**-Assistant Professor, Department of Public Administration, University of Sindh, Jamshoro, Pakistan-⁽⁴⁾**Mohammad Ali Pasha Panhwar**-Lecturer, Department of Economics, University of Sindh, Jamshoro, Pakistan

Abstract

The research on employee job satisfaction is wide area of the management science but it need to work for its determinants, in this connection the study of career commitment and job satisfaction was carried out in the commercial banking sector of Sukkur region @ sukkur, Sindh, Pakistan, data was collected through the questionnaire and administered personally, for checking the relationship SPSS was used, at first instance the reliability analysis of the data collection instrument was checked and followed by exploratory factor analysis, linear regression, and Pearson (1-tailed) correlation was checked. The results suggested that over all model is not fit because the career commitment is not completely predicting the job satisfaction but the significant, and the strength of relation of career commitment with job satisfaction was not powerful but the significant.

Key Words: Career Commitment, Employee Job Satisfaction, Organizational Commitment, Career Commitment Measure.

Introduction

In today's competitive environment financial service providers needs to "sustain and flourish" keeping in view this need motivate commercial banks to the platform where people are considered as an asset to their organization, not the burden for paying the salaries only. Work force is considered to be the backbone of service organizations, and this is the part of contemporary human resource management. People can be an asset for their organization only when they are committed to their organization and career. Employees who are committed to their career clarify before their employer to decide that the employee is an asset or not is a career commitment. Numerous career switching is observed in commercial banks, because banking sector is offering career growth and career opportunities. While having expertise in baking (banker) can be human resource officer, sales promotion officer, teller, public relation officer agricultural expert, loaning manager, accountant, electronic banking expert, an attorney, an economist, a computer programmer, operations manager, e t c. as in banking sector there are many career opportunities, so it is easy to switch from career to another, so for as working environment is

concerned for improving the commitment of employees to their careers.

Objectives of the Study

Objective of this research is to analyze the role of career commitment in employee job satisfaction of the employees working in commercial banking sector.

Literature Review

Career commitment is the attitude of one person to its profession (Blau, 1985; Goulet & Singh, 2002) concluded that job security, job satisfaction and organizational commitment are positively related to career commitment. Study conducted by Iqbal (2010) the length of service is significantly related to the organizational commitment, and he further stated that managers and supervisors are more committed than other workers. According to Chang (1999) the people who have some sort of expectations regarding their employment and if those perceived expectations for his job was fulfilled by the authorities than he/she will have higher career commitment. There are number of factors affecting on need and expectations of individual from his job and satisfaction derived

from work which finally leads to the career commitment.

According to London's 1983, career motivation theory evaluate the effects of individuals, situations, and extra work variables on career commitment. These three points are:

1. Individual variables: "Needs, Interest and personality variables potentially relevant to one's career. These dimensions are clustered in to three domains: career insight, career identity, and career resilience". (p. 620).
2. Situational variables: work environment factors can influence career motivation, such as "staffing policies and procedures, leadership style, job design, group cohesiveness, career development programs, and the compensation system". (p. 621).
3. Extra Work variables: these are mostly related to the demand of work and family. (p.621).

Carson & Badenian (1994) published a paper on career commitment: construction of measure and examination of its psychometric properties. They setup a measurement as a result of (Blau, 1985; Colarelli & Bishop, 1990) scales. The new creation was known as Career Commitment Measure, (CCM).

Job satisfaction focuses on the role of employees in the work place. Thus job satisfaction as affective orientation on the individuals towards the regulations of work roles which they are occupying (Vroom, 1964). According to Armstrong (2006) job satisfaction is a attitude and feeling of people about their work. Positive and favourable attitude towards their job is the indication of job satisfaction and viceversa.

According to Christen, Lyer, & Soberman (2006) they suggested a model of satisfaction comprises of some elements: job related factors, role perceptions,

job performance, and firm performance. Layler & Porter (1967) suggested their model of job satisfaction with unlike the previous model which place the importance as the impact of reward system on job satisfaction, according to them extrinsic and intrinsic rewards are not directly linked with the job satisfaction, because of employees perceptions about the deserved pay level. Locke & Lathan (1990), they suggested some different model of job satisfaction. They started from an assumption that the objectives are settled at highest level and high expectations for success in work provide achievements and success in performing the task.

Sampling Design

Sampling for this study comprises of management and officer level employees of different public and private sector commercial banks of sukkur region, sindh, Pakistan.

Data Collection Method

A questionnaire was designed for collection of primary data from above sample: questionnaire comprises of 34 questions related to job satisfaction and career commitment, each response alternative was based on 5 point likert scale. The said questionnaire was administered personally and it was pretested first from the 10 respondents of Habib Bank Limited, Shah Abdul Latif University Branch, before administering it to all the sample.

Statistical Method

In order to check the impact of the variables Reliability analysis was used by checking the cronbach's alpha, of the data collection instrument through SPSS, Regression and Pearson Correlation analysis was used to check the strength of relationship among variables, either positive or negative, and how much each variable is correlated (highly, average, not related) with otherone.

Results and Discussions

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.802	34

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.380 ^a	.145	.128	.93370229

a. Predictors: (Constant), Career Commitment

Model summary table states about the equation of regression about the model of job satisfaction as dependent and career commitment as independent variable, constant of equation Alpha and the error term, and looking at the value of Adjusted R-square that is .128, means the only independent variable of career commitment is not predicting the dependent variable but more the error term is in the equation which needs to work out for the other independent variables for reduction of error term, but the overall model fit “adjusted R-square” is significant at .005 level.

Analysis of Variance

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	7.666	1	7.666	8.794	.005 ^a
	Residual	45.334	52	.872		
	Total	53.000	53			

This table again represents the regression equation, contribution of independent variable and the remaining error term which is not attained by the regression equation.

Coefficients

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	-3.671E-17	.127		.000	1.000
	Career Commitment	.380	.128	.380	2.965	.005

a. Dependent Variable: Job Satisfaction

Standardized beta of career commitment is in positive sign and it is .380, which means career commitment is positively related to the employee job satisfaction but the strength of relationship is not too much strong or simply we can say that it is weak, but significant.

Correlation

	Job Satisfaction	Career Commitment
Job Satisfaction Pearson Correlation Significant	1	.380* .002
Career Commitment Pearson Correlation Significant	.380* .002	1

According to the results of Pearson (1-tailed) correlation job satisfaction and career commitment is significantly correlated with each other but not strongly, this situation needs to work out in future to find out other variables to predict the job satisfaction completely as per the need of hour.

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